

Structural Structure of Innovative Activity of Preschool Educational Organization

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Abstract: The article explains the content of the concepts of innovation, innovative activity, innovative organization. Also, the main directions and structural structures of innovative activities in the organization of preschool education were discussed. In particular, the main aspects and directions of innovative management in the system of preschool education organizations are covered in detail.

Keywords: Preschool Organization, Innovation, Personal Upbringing, Innovative Activity, Innovative Process, Innovative Potential, Innovation, Innovative Technologies.

1. Introduction

The developments taking place in our country, in turn, have affected the organization of preschool education. In particular, from 2018, the work aimed at developing the organization of preschool education is reflected in the decisions and laws issued in this area. According to the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 30, 2018 No PP-3955 "On measures to improve the management of preschool education" strengthening, providing them with qualified teaching staff, the introduction of modern educational programs and technologies in the educational process of comprehensive intellectual, spiritual, aesthetic and physical development of children, radically improving their level of school readiness. As a logical continuation of this decision, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 8, 2019 No PP-4312 "On approval of the Concept of development of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" was adopted.

2. The Main Results and Findings

Over the past period, a large-scale work has been carried out in our country to create an effective system of preschool education aimed at bringing up the younger generation in a healthy and comprehensive maturity, the introduction of effective forms and methods of teaching in the educational process.

New methods or innovations are inherent in any human activity, and therefore have naturally become the subject of study, analysis, and application. Innovations do not arise spontaneously, they are formed on the basis of the results of scientific research, the advanced skills of pedagogical teams in individual children and the whole preschool organization. This process cannot be spontaneous, it is defined by the need for management. I. Ojegov's dictionary interprets the new word as follows: "Newly created or made, now re-discovered in the place of the previous, re-discovered in the recent past or in the present, not yet sufficiently studied, unknown" [6].

The philosophical encyclopedic dictionary is development-oriented, has laws, and is described as a necessary change. The term "innovation" translates from Latin to mean "renewal, innovation or change". This concept first appeared in nineteenth-century research, meaning the incorporation of elements (components) of one culture into another. At the beginning of the twentieth century, a new field of knowledge - innovation, the science of innovation - emerged, within which the laws of technical innovation in the field of material production began to be studied. Pedagogical innovative processes in preschool education have been the subject of special research in the West in the 1950s and in Russia over the last two decades.

In pedagogical theory, there are some discrepancies based on the definitions of different authors (innovation, novelty, new procedures).

According to the first view, the Russian authors (G.M. Kodjaspirova, A.Yu. Kodjaspirov, S.A. Barannikova, etc.) believe that the words "novelty, new procedures, innovation" are synonymous with each other believe that [3]. Here V.N. Kuzmin, I.P. Podlasyy, L.V. Pozdnyak et al. [7]

Proponents of the second approach (K.Yu.Belaya, S.F.Bagautdinova, V.S.Lazarev, A.V.Lorensov, M.M.Potashnik, O.G.Khomeriki and others, grouped these concepts and called them “new-. innovation ”,“ innovation-innovation introduction ”[1]. Innovation is a new tool, a new method, style, technology, program, etc. Innovation is a process of mastering these tools. goal-directed change by introducing new robust components (innovations) into the environment, causing the system to move from one state to another.

In describing the "innovation process" K.Yu. Belaya, V.S. Lazarev, MM Potashnik use the category "activity". The innovation process is the creation, assimilation, use and promotion of innovations [2]. Despite some differences in the views of scientists, the general basis of the concepts of "innovation", "innovation" and "innovation" is the development of the object under study as a result of the introduction of new components.

It should be noted that some researchers and practitioners associate innovative activity only with experimental activity. The other part of the researchers. (SF Bagautdinova and others) give a broader interpretation of the concept of "innovative activity", which includes "the introduction of advanced pedagogical experience, the application of scientific research in practice, experimental activities, the introduction of innovations" [8].

These concepts are the content of the most current educational process organization technologies, widely used in various fields. In recent years, new concepts have emerged: an innovative educational institution, an innovative oligarch, and so on. innovation management, innovation management, management innovation and more. We will consider in detail the following categories: innovative educational institution, innovative activity management, management innovation, innovative management.

It should be noted that innovative activities in the organization of preschool education are unique. In particular, in order to form innovative skills in the person of the future educator, it is necessary, first of all, theoretical and motivational training to master the innovations in the field, as well as the formation of modern technologies and databases. At the same time, there is a strong desire to create new practical ideas or paradigms and developments of research, popularization of knowledge, skills, experience of qualified educators and enrichment of the existing methodological base with innovations.

“Innovative preschool education has the following features: a model of organizing the life of a child different from public educational institutions is developed and implemented, the unique structure of the work aimed at developing the creative personality of the teacher is explored, new methods and tools are tested [5].

The development of an educational institution (that is, its transition to a new, high-quality state) will not be possible without the introduction of innovations and the development of the innovation process. In order to manage innovative activities, the head of an educational institution must understand and study its structure and structure.

Scheme 1. Views of the main activities of the preschool education organization

The development of preschool education organizations is in the form of a complex dynamic system, so innovative activity (as a system) is politically structured, and it can be divided into the following structural components: active, subjective, hierarchical, meaningful, managerial, organizational [9].

The structure of activity is a set of the following components: motives, goals, objectives, meaningful structure, form, methods, results. The subjective structure includes the innovative activities of all participants in the educational process: the manager, their deputies, teachers, students, parents, etc. According to the hierarchical structure, innovative activity in the institution should cover all stages of the subject of management: international, republican, regional, district and school. The meaningful structure of the innovation process requires the development and adoption of innovations in all areas of the educational process, in the management of MTT. The lack of management of the innovation process in the educational institution leads to its rapid extinction, so the existence of a management structure does not negate even parts of self-governance, serving as a stabilizing and supporting factor in this process. The organizational structure of the innovation process includes the following stages: diagnostic - prognostic - organizing - practical - generalizing - implementing.

All the structural parts of innovative activity in preschool education organizations are inextricably linked with each other. The importance and necessity is that all of them are implemented in parallel and simultaneously, which allows for the effective development of the educational institution. The organization of preschool education as an independent organism has a very complex structure, which includes the following components: a set of goals, activities that ensure their implementation; the community of adults and children who form and participate in the community; their unifying relationship; internal and external environment; management that ensures the integration of all components into the integrity, its targeted functionality and development. In this sense, the fact that innovations apply to all components, as well as bring to life an innovative process with different characteristics. That is why scientists classify all innovations into specific types based on different methodological bases.

Management of preschool education with the theory of categorization of innovations and innovations studied by SF Bagautdinova, K.Yu. Belaya, LV Pozdnyak and other researchers [7].

L.V. Pozdnyak's typology is of interest, it is a completely new criterion that does not exist in any typology of preschool education in terms of its potential for innovation, the mechanism of its implementation, size and results - the peculiarities of the innovation process.

Innovative potential in the organization of preschool education, according to LV Pozdnyak, distinguishes the following innovations: radical, mixed, modified;

- According to the mechanisms of implementation: primary-diffusion; completed - unfinished; successful-unsuccessful;
- by size, goals, social consequences: point, system, multiple, strategic.

According to the peculiarities of the innovation process: absolute novelty (no analogues); relative novelty (local, these preschools, in this area); goal-oriented innovation [7].

The modern leader of the preschool organization should know the classification of innovations, first of all, to understand the object of development of the kindergarten, to define a comprehensive description of the acquired innovations, to understand the commonalities and differences, and to develop the technology of its mastering.

To date, the following scheme of development of innovative activities in the field of scientific literature in social organizations, including preschool education (school, kindergarten) [4]:

1. Identify the need for innovation and the emergence of the idea of such innovation; conditionally is the stage of invention, which is the result (or instantaneous emergence) of fundamental and applied scientific research.
2. Invention, that is, the creation of a material or spiritual product-pattern and novelty, reflected in any subject. This includes developing, creating and mastering innovation first.
3. At the innovation stage, the innovation is applied in practice and its additional development is carried out; This phase is completed by obtaining a solid effect from the innovation. After that, the independent "life" of the novelty begins, the process of introducing the novelty goes to the next stage only if there is a sensitivity to the novelty.
4. Dissemination of innovation, its widespread implementation and distribution in new areas.
5. The dominance of innovation in a particular field is lost over time, and this stage becomes an effective alternative, or this innovation is replaced by a newer and more effective one.
6. The reduction in the scope of application of the innovation is associated with its replacement by a newer product.

3. Conclusion

Any pedagogical innovation is a process that develops in space and time, combining ideas and technologies based on objective laws and practical experience of research. In many cases, the news is that individual educators seek to overcome the obstacles that arise by using progressive trends that are understood or intuitive. However, for innovation to thrive, formal support is needed to implement its scientific development and fundamentals.

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